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**„International Conference of Experimental and
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Sponsored by:

**MINISTRY OF EDUCATION, SCIENCE AND TECHNICAL DEVELOPMENT
OF THE REPUBLIC OF SERBIA**

**Programme
and
The Book of Abstracts**

02-05 July 2019

Zlatibor, Serbia

SEMI-QUANTITATIVE ASSESSMENT OF SALIVARY GLAND FUNCTION IN PATIENTS WITH DIFFERENTIATED THYROID CARCINOMA AFTER RADIOIODINE THERAPY

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Abstract

Objective: Radioiodine-¹³¹I therapy (RAIT) has been established as an effective treatment for differentiated thyroid carcinoma (DTC). One of the most common complications is salivary gland damage, associated with early and late-onset complications. This prospective study was conducted to determine the effect of RAIT on the function of salivary glands using ^{99m}Tc-pertechnetate scintigraphy.

Methods: Twenty five patients with post-surgical DTC were referred for RAIT. Before and 4-6 months after RAIT, salivary gland scintigraphy with ^{99m}Tc-pertechnetate was performed. Regions of interest were drawn over the parotid and submandibular glands and respective backgrounds. Time-activity curves were generated and semiquantitative functional parameters, were calculated: maximum uptake fraction (MUF) and excretion fraction (EF).

Results: When compared between pre-ablation and post-ablation, MUF of bilateral parotid and submandibular glands were significantly increased ($p < 0.001$ and $p = 0.040$ respectively). Mean EF, for parotid glands was reduced as compared to baseline measurements ($p = 0.003$). When compared between pre-ablation and post-ablation, EF for submandibular glands were significantly decreased ($p = 0.042$). The semiquantitative scintigraphic analyses showed functional deficits with greater involvement of the parotid glands. There was not a significant positive correlation between the given ¹³¹I dose and salivary glands impairment.

Conclusion: The semiquantitative scintigraphy analysis showed damage to the parotid and submandibular glands. Therefore, more emphasis should be placed on salivary gland dysfunction during follow-up for DTC patients.

Keywords

radioiodine therapy, differentiated thyroid carcinoma, salivary glands